

Factors Affecting Customers 'Satisfaction For Phu Quoc Fish Sauce Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to evaluate the factors affecting customer satisfaction when using Phu Quoc fish sauce. The author conducted an analysis on 696 consumers of Phu Quoc fish sauce in Vietnam, the results showed that factors positively impact the satisfaction of Phu Quoc lucky consumers such as product quality, price. Both products

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Phu Quoc fish sauce, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Socio-economy is increasingly developing, human needs are increasing day by day. Understanding and understanding the needs of people is something that any administrator wants.

In fact, there are no executives so talented that they can understand the changing needs of people over time. To know and understand exactly the present time people need, one way is to investigate.

The competition in the market is getting more and more fierce, the companies compete very fiercely with each other. Every company wants to sell the most products. In this situation, any company that has the support of consumers will win this fierce battle. Therefore, the evaluation of customer satisfaction with the Company's products is very important and essential for the survival of a business.

Vietnam has a coastline stretching from the North to the South, seafood is an abundant and abundant source of raw materials. Taking advantage of that, our country's food technology industry is investing to expand production with modern technology lines. Including fish sauce production industry. Fish sauce is an indispensable spice in the kitchen and on the dining table of most Vietnamese families. The characteristic aromatic flavor enhances the palatability of the meal. Since ancient times, grandparents used to keep fish and salt in jars, after a few months produced a dark red water, the strong smell of sea fish, the taste is very salty. Those are very typical characteristics of fish sauce.

Fish sauce is a protein solution which is mainly amino acids, formed by the hydrolysis of fish protein thanks to the protease enzyme system in fish. Fish sauce has high nutritional value (in the sauce contains about 13 types of amino acids, B vitamins, about 1-5 micrograms of vitamin B12), appealing to consumers because of the rich flavor that no other product can. instead of, replace. In addition, fish sauce is also used to treat a number of illnesses such as stomachache, burns, body weakness, energy supply.

People who make fish sauce are familiar to the people of the sea, but to get a good kind of fish sauce, eat once to remember life, few people can do it. Occupation of our country's fish sauce is still under the traditional method, in each locality there is a little difference, but the production process is still rudimentary and prolonged time, economic efficiency is low. There have been many studies gradually mechanizing fish sauce but still limited due to the corrosion of salt on metals.

2. Literature review

2.1. Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction has become an important asset for businesses and organizations in their efforts to improve service quality, maintain loyalty and enhance their competitiveness. In 1989, the first customer satisfaction index (barometer) was launched in Sweden (Swedish Customer Satisfaction Barometer - SCSB) to establish a customer satisfaction index for product purchase and consumption. domestic service. In the following years, this index was developed and widely applied in developed countries such as the US - ACSI, Norway - NCSI, Denmark - DCSI and EU - ECSI countries. This index can be done on the national level (how businesses and

industries will be satisfied with their customers) or from an industry perspective (comparing the satisfaction of enterprises in the industry). scope of an industry) and compare between different times (to see a change). From there, businesses can know the position and appreciation of customers for businesses to set business goals and strategies.

2.2. Factors affecting customer satisfaction

According to Zeithaml and Bitner (1996), customer satisfaction is influenced by the following key factors: service quality; product quality; price (price); situational factors and personal factors.

Service quality is the most important factor affecting customer satisfaction (Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Yavas et al, 1997; Ahmad and Kamal, 2002). If a service provider provides customers with quality products that meet their needs, that business has initially made customer satisfaction. In other words, service quality and customer satisfaction are closely related (positive relationship), in which service quality is what is created first and then determines satisfaction. of customer. The causal relationship between these two factors is a key issue in most customer satisfaction studies. In the study of the relationship between these two factors, Spreng and Mackoy (1996) also showed that service quality is the premise of customer satisfaction.

3. Research method

The framework of choice theory research is a model of Srivastava & Kaul (2014); Moriuchi & Takahashi (2016) when giving the factors affecting customer satisfaction: Experience of purchasing, price, advertising sales; together with the study of Szymanski & Hise (2000) with the convenience factor.

Research models

Analytical techniques

The reliability of the scale was assessed through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and item-total correlation coefficient. These two criteria help measure how closely the observed variables in the scale correlate with each other.

Regarding the value of Cronbach alpha, Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2008) said: "Many researchers agree that this value is from 0.8 up to near 1, the scale is good, from 0, 7 to 0.8 is usable. There are also researchers who suggest that Cronbach alpha of 0.6 or higher is usable in case the concept of measurement scale is new or new to respondents in the context of the study (Nunnally, 1978) ". In this study, the author only uses scales for which the Cronbach alpha coefficient has a value of 0.6 or higher. (Hair et al., 2006)

For scales with a Cronbach Alpha coefficient less than 0.6, the scale is inappropriate and consider certain types of observed variables to achieve a better Cronbach Alpha coefficient. Note that the observed

variables for Cronbach Alpha test must ensure 3 or more variables. If it is less than performing a scale verification, the software will not make any recommendations about assessing the scale.

The total variable correlation coefficient represents the correlation between one observed variable and all other variables in the scale. The higher the coefficient, the higher the correlation of the variable with other variables. Variables with a correlation coefficient of variables greater than 0.3 are considered appropriate, with observed variables having a total correlation coefficient of less than 0.3 are considered as garbage variables and removed from the scale. (Nunally & Burstein, 1994).

To test the hypotheses, the regression analysis method will be used. The regression estimation method between dependent variables and the independent variables in the model uses the method of least squares (OLS).

The standardized linear regression model has the following form:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i + \dots + \beta_k X_k + U_i$$

In which the:

Y is a dependent variable

β_0 is the blocking factor (constant)

The X_i is the independent variable

β_i is the slope - reflects the influence of variable X_i on the dependent variable Y.

U_i is the random or also known as noise is the variation of the dependent variable Y affected in addition to the variables X_i included in the model.

4. Research results

With 696 questionnaires for fish sauce users in Vietnam, women accounted for nearly 5 times the number of men (82.3% of women and men of 15.6%). The age group from 25 to 35 accounts for the majority with 417 people accounting for 58.6%; followed by people aged 35-45 with 219 people accounting for 30.8%. Educational attainment of the survey subjects are mainly colleges and universities; in which college degree accounts for the largest proportion with 45.1% and university level accounts for 34.6%. The income of the surveyed people is mainly from 15 to 25 million with 360 people accounting for 50.6%; The proportion of income above 35 million is at least with 3%. The number of people in the household is mainly 4 people with 258 people accounting for 36.3%, followed by the number of 3 people in the household with 174 people accounting for 24.5%. Regarding the frequency of buying mainly 2 times per month with 186 people accounting for 78.5%. the number of one time or less than 1 time per month is 13.9% and over 2 times 1 month is only 5.1%. In terms of volume used, most types of volume used are from 250 to 500ml with 513 people accounting for 71.2%; followed by the volume from 500-750ml with 129 people accounting for 18.1%. Regarding prices of fish sauce, the most popular ones are VND 30,000 with 489 people, accounting for 68.8% and VND 60,000 with 147 people, accounting for 20.7%.

Table 1: reliability scale

	Cronbach's Alpha	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SEN1	.663	.203	.728
SEN2		.480	.589
SEN3		.626	.455
SEN4		.529	.539
FEEL1	.179	.208	.104
FEEL2		.256	.078
FEEL3		.137	.740
FEEL1	.744	.593	-

	Cronbach's Alpha	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
FEEL2		.593	-
THINK1	.774	.359	.817
THINK2		.664	.677
THINK3		.645	.681
THINK4		.659	.672
RELA1	.761	.406	.775
RELA2		.653	.657
RELA3		.647	.653
RELA4		.557	.709
PRI1	.750	.595	.651
PRI2		.631	.605
PRI3		.518	.746
PRO1	.619	.346	.627
PRO2		.515	.392
PRO3		.446	.505
QUA1	.728	.529	.664
QUA2		.536	.656
QUA3		.479	.691
QUA4		.533	.658
SAT1	.777	.554	.738
SAT2		.587	.721
SAT3		.609	.709
SAT4		.579	.726

The factor analysis results are suitable for KMO coefficient greater than 0.5; The p-value of Barlett's test is less than 0.05 and the explanatory variance is greater than 50%. The results show that there are 4 factors formed similar to the hypothesis.

Table 2. Result of factor analysis belongs to Image and brand

	Main ingredient			
	1	2	3	4
RELA2	.691			
RELA3	.662			
RELA4	.647			
RELA1	.584			
THINK2		.751		
THINK1		.695		
THINK4		.609		
THINK3		.603		
SEN2			.750	
SEN3			.712	
SEN4			.697	
FEEL2				.839
FEEL1				.814

KMO		0.86	
p-value Barlett test		0.0000	
Variance explained		65.50%	

The factor analysis results are suitable for KMO coefficient greater than 0.5; The p-value of the Barlett test is less than 0.05 and the explanatory variance is greater than 50%. The results show that there are 3 factors formed similar to the hypothesis.

Table 3. Results of factor analysis for advertising, product quality and price

	Main ingredient		
	1	2	3
QUA2	.767		
QUA4	.719		
QUA3	.642		
QUA1	.618		
PRI1		.834	
PRI2		.822	
PRI3		.594	
PRO2			.833
PRO3			.676
PRO1			.651
KMO			.833
p-value Barlett test			.000
Variance explained			60.25%

The factor analysis results are suitable for KMO coefficient greater than 0.5; The p-value of the Barlett test is less than 0.05 and the explanatory variance is greater than 50%. The results show that there is a factor formed similar to the hypothesis.

Table 3. Results of factor analysis for satisfaction

	Main ingredient
	1
SAT3	.791
SAT2	.784
SAT4	.770
SAT1	.755
KMO	0.714
p-value Barlett test	0.000
Variance explained	60.04%

The correlation table results show that the variables are all correlated with each other at the 1% significance level. At the same time, the correlation coefficient is positive, showing that the variables have a reciprocal relationship with each other. However, the author conducted regression analysis to find the true causal relationship between the factors according to the research model.

Table 4. Results of correlation analysis

	SEN	FEEL	THINK	RELA	PRI	PRO	QUA	SAT
SEN	1							
FEEL	.189**	1						
THINK	.533**	.240**	1					
RELA	.566**	.274**	.571**	1				
PRI	.493**	.174*	.452**	.586**	1			
PRO	.346**	.253**	.413**	.500**	.312**	1		

QUA	.436**	.211**	.532**	.597**	.541**	.445**	1	
SAT	.419**	.189**	.339**	.469**	.421**	.419**	.498**	1
**. There is a significant correlation 1%								
*. There is a significant correlation 5%								

The regression results show that convenience has a positive effect on buying experience (p-value is less than 0.05 and beta is positive)

Table 5. Results of analyzing the impact of PRO on image and brand factors

	Not standardized beta		Standardized coefficient	t	p-value	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Dependent variable: SEN						
(Constant)	2.158	.258		8.420	.000	
PRO	.466	.068	.438	6.981	.000	1.000
Dependent variable: FEEL						
(Constant)	1.318	.849		1.552	.122	
PRO	.691	.222	.212	3.108	.002	1.000
Dependent variable: THINK						
(Constant)	1.545	.248		6.236	.000	1.000
PRO	.586	.065	.536	9.064	.000	
Dependent variable: RELA						
(Constant)	1.526	.222		6.871	.000	1.000
PRO	.626	.058	.598	10.721	.000	

With a VIF of less than 10, this phenomenon does not occur in the author's research model. Therefore, it is reasonable to include independent variables at the same time. The regression results show that out of the seven hypothetical factors, only 3 factors have a positive impact on satisfaction including: SEN; PRO and CON. The other four variables are: FELL; THINK; RELA; PRI has no effect on satisfaction (p-value is greater than 0.05)

Table 6. Result of analyzing the impact of factors on satisfaction

	Not standardized beta		Standardized coefficient	t	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	.632	.304		2.066	.040	
SEN	.166	.076	.168	2.249	.026	1.695
FEEL	.007	.018	.029	.467	.641	1.111
THINK	-.076	.076	-.076	-1.018	.310	1.795
RELA	.093	.082	.093	1.117	.265	2.345
PRI	.116	.075	.115	1.515	.131	1.753
PRO	.208	.079	.189	2.753	.006	1.448
QUA	.272	.086	.256	3.319	.001	1.878
Dependent variable: SAT						

5. Conclusion

Senses that have a positive effect on customer satisfaction show that when customers feel about the smell, color and taste when eating well, they will make them more satisfied. The aroma will stimulate the user's sense of smell to make them feel more appealing and eager to taste. Next is the use area, from the smell towards the rich flavor to make customers feel satisfied with their needs. Therefore, creating the aroma for fish sauce and strong flavor makes customers more satisfied when using it. Besides, the natural color factor also makes

customers have a visual reaction. With fish sauce has natural colors make them feel good with health and close to nature.

Next the advertising media program also has a positive impact on customer satisfaction when using fish sauce. Product introduction programs that increase in frequency with customers will make customers know or understand fish sauce more. From there, they will feel more satisfied when using this brand. Customers who use products that they know about the brand or supplier will make them feel safe and lead to greater satisfaction. In addition, promotional programs on incentives bring more satisfaction to customers. With brands that consumers already know, preferential sales programs will bring a sense of closeness and interest from suppliers. Therefore, they feel more satisfied when the supplier cares about the customers themselves.

Product quality has a positive impact on customer satisfaction, which makes buying fish sauce even easier will make customers feel more satisfied. The ease of finding products around customers' areas will save time and effort for purchasing grasping water. Easy to find products that not only save on buying fish sauce but also make customers see the popularity of Phu Quoc fish sauce. A popular product makes customers feel more confident in many places and especially when used by many people. At the same time with diverse categories, customers will have many options to suit their financial and needs. Customers will be more comfortable when not having to buy fish sauce bottles with capacities that are not suitable for their families (too small volume, or prefer plastic bottles than glass bottles), so it's easy to choose and diversify products will make customers more satisfied.

At the same time, the regression results also show that convenience has a positive impact on 4 factors of brand and image. This result indicates that buying and using fish sauce conveniently makes customers' evaluation of the color and taste of the fish sauce as possible; The easy access to Phu Quoc fish sauce makes customers have a better sense of the product.

The remaining factors have no impact on customer satisfaction also indicate some of the following characteristics:

The perception factor about the reliability of Phu Quoc fish sauce does not affect the satisfaction, this indicates that the information about Phu Quoc fish sauce (distributor of origin) is well known by the people so the supply Providing information on Phu Quoc fish sauce seems to be unnecessary to enhance customer satisfaction. In addition, the product sauce on the packaging with full information is mandatory, so the reliability of the origin as well as the ingredients of the brands is the same, so does not affect customer satisfaction.

Factors think about fish sauce in life has no impact on customer satisfaction. Because the sauce factor is that Vietnamese people have become familiar with families, this is an indispensable spice in families. In addition, in Quang Ninh, Phu Quoc fish sauce produced here should be widely used and popular among families, so with Phu Quoc fish sauce, they consider it a local product and a mandatory product. have in the family so they are more dissatisfied when people advertise about the role of fish sauce in the family. The connection between individuals and people who are interested in using Phu Quoc fish sauce also does not affect satisfaction. of customer. Because the surveyed area is also the province that produces Phu Quoc fish sauce, people in this area mainly use Phu Quoc fish sauce.

Price perception factor also has no impact on customer satisfaction about Phu Quoc fish sauce. According to the survey, Phu Quoc fish sauce used in the survey area was purchased at competitive prices and lower than other brands of fish sauce of the same content and volume. Therefore, the lower price adjustment does not make customers more satisfied when the price is more favorable and the quality is more richer.

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